

REJUVENATING OUT-OF-DATE PRE-PREGS WITH IMINE-EPOXY VITRIMERS

Sharine Noelle O. Bendulo¹, Houlei Gan², Juan Zhang³, Russell J. Varley²

¹Institute for Frontier Materials, Deakin University
75 Pigdons Rd, Waurn Ponds, Victoria, Australia

Email: s219444715@deakin.edu.au, sobendulo@gmail.com Web page: <https://www.deakin.edu.au>

²School of Engineering, RMIT University
124 La Trobe St., Melbourne, Victoria, Australia

³Institute for Polymer Composites, Jiangsu University of Technology
1801 Zhongwu St., Changzhou 213001, Jiangsu, China

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ABSTRACT

Composites have a strength-to-weight ratio, approximately nine times that of steel, making them desirable for demanding applications such as in wind turbine blades, aircraft and automobiles. However, their commercial viability is constrained by logistical challenges, including the necessity for refrigerated transport and storage, as well as their inability to be molded or welded post-curing. Carbon fiber pre-pregs require refrigeration and must be maintained in a frozen state until use, complicating logistics and increasing waste due to spoilage during power outages. This study investigates the potential of vitrimers as a solution to rejuvenate out-of-date or improperly cured pre-pregs. Vitrimers are crosslinked polymer networks modified with dynamic bonds that undergo bond exchange reactions at elevated temperatures. This results in material flow which enables thermoforming and bonding even after curing which is not possible for existing thermosets. In this work, carbon fiber pre-pregs based on diglycidyl ether of bisphenol A, DGEBA, are cured to varying degrees of cure, and cured with an already fully cured imine-containing epoxy vitrimer, *p*VAPI-DETDA. The mechanical and thermal properties of the resulting laminates were characterized through three-point bending tests, dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA), thermogravimetric analysis (TGA), differential scanning calorimetry (DSC), and microscopy. The laminates demonstrated high glass transition temperatures of up to 177°C, degradation temperatures reaching 387°C, flexural strengths up to 1.31 GPa, and flexural moduli up to 105 GPa. These findings suggest that vitrimers can significantly mitigate waste and energy consumption while addressing the logistical limitations associated with thermoset carbon fiber pre-pregs. Moreover, this approach could enable the transport of composites similar to sheet metals, eliminating the need for refrigeration and enhancing their commercial potential.

1 INTRODUCTION

Fiber-reinforced polymer composites (FRPs) are advanced hybrid materials composed of a reinforcement—commonly fibers such as carbon, glass, or natural fibers—and a matrix, which can be a thermoset or thermoplastic polymer, ceramic, or metal.¹ Among these, carbon fiber-reinforced polymer (CFRP) composites are particularly attractive due to their high strength-to-weight ratio, excellent thermal stability, and mechanical robustness. These attributes make them ideal for aircraft structures, vehicle components, and wind turbine blades.¹⁻⁴

CFRPs can be manufactured using various techniques, including hand lay-up, vacuum infusion, compression molding, and prepreg processing. Prepregs—fibers pre-impregnated with a polymer resin—are widely used, especially in the aerospace industry.⁵⁻⁸ These prepregs are typically stored and transported in a frozen state to inhibit premature curing. Upon reaching the end user, they are

maintained under cold storage conditions until they are laid up in molds and consolidated under heat and pressure into the desired composite structure. For instance, aerospace manufacturers such as Boeing receive large rolls of prepregs that are kept frozen until final forming, requiring energy-intensive logistics. However, challenges arise when there are disruptions such as power outages or transportation delays.⁹ In such cases, premature curing reactions between the epoxide and amine components may initiate, resulting in increased stiffness or boardiness of the prepreg. Boardy prepregs indicate partial cure, which reduces the availability of reactive functional groups essential for good interfacial bonding during composite formation. In severe cases where the prepregs are nearly or fully cured, they become non-adherent and unsuitable for further processing, leading to disposal and material wastage. This issue is rooted in the inherent intractability of thermosets, whose permanent crosslinked networks cannot be reshaped or remolded once cured.

To address this problem, the use of vitrimers is proposed—a class of crosslinked polymers that incorporate dynamic covalent bonds, enabling network rearrangement under specific conditions. Unlike conventional thermosets, vitrimers can exhibit thermoplastic-like flow behavior at elevated temperatures due to dynamic bond exchange reactions that facilitate topological reconfiguration. This property allows vitrimers to interdiffuse and entangle across interfaces, forming strong bonds even with thermosets. Furthermore, when vitrimers possess complementary functional groups, they can form covalent linkages with unreacted groups on partially cured prepreg surfaces, enabling chemical rejuvenation. Remarkably, vitrimers can achieve such interactions even when fully cured, offering post-curing reprocessability and welding capability.¹⁰⁻¹³

In this study, we exploited the weldability and reprocessability of an epoxy vitrimer based on dynamic imine bonds to rejuvenate out-of-date thermoset prepregs and maintain usability despite their boardy nature. Specifically, the initial cure state, i.e., the availability of residual functional groups affects vitrimer-assisted recovery. Thermoset prepregs of varying cure levels were interleaved with fully cured vitrimer single plies derived from *p*VAPI-DETDA, a vitrimer from an imine-epoxide synthesized from vanillin and 4-aminophenol, and the amine hardener diethyltoluenediamine (DETDA), and hot-pressed into laminates. The resulting materials were characterized using differential scanning calorimetry (DSC), dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA), thermogravimetric analysis (TGA), and flexural testing to evaluate thermal and mechanical performance. Our results confirm that the vitrimer can effectively rejuvenate prepregs with sufficient unreacted functional groups by enabling covalent bonding. In cases where functional group availability is limited, vitrimer chain diffusion and physical entanglement still result in moderate property recovery. This study demonstrates that imine-epoxy vitrimers can extend the usability of out-of-date or improperly cured prepregs, offering a sustainable route to reduce composite material waste and retain performance.

2 METHODOLOGY

2.1 Sample Preparation

The vanillin-based imine-containing epoxide monomer was synthesized according to the method reported by Zhao, et al. (2018).¹³ The resulting imine-epoxide, *p*VAPI epoxide, was then mixed with diethyltoluenediamine (DETDA) in a 1:1.5 ratio and dissolved in dichloromethane. Unidirectional carbon fibers were then impregnated with the mixture, the solvent was removed, vacuum bagged, and then cured in an oven at 120°C for 2 hours, 150°C for 2 hours and 177°C for 5 hours under vacuum. Thermoset prepregs were prepared from diglycidyl ether of bisphenol A (DGEBA) and DETDA in a 1:0.9 ratio. Unidirectional carbon fibers were impregnated with the mixture, vacuum bagged, and processed accordingly. Partially cured and fully prepregs were cured in an oven at 80°C and 150°C for 6 hours, respectively. As benchmark for out-of-date prepregs, a fresh uncured prepreg was prepared. This was done to simulate different stages of cure of improperly cured or out-of-date prepregs.

Figure 1: Images of (a) uncured, (b) partially cured and (c) fully cured DGEBA-DETDA carbon fibre prepregs and (d) fully cured *p*VAPI-DETDA carbon fibre prepreg.

Laminates designated as Unc VTCF, Par VTCF, and Ful VTCF, were then prepared from 8 alternating layers of uncured, partially cured and fully cured DGEBA-DETDA pre-pregs, respectively, with fully cured *p*VAPI-DETDA vitrimer single plies. The consolidation was done in a hot press at 200°C for 3 hours as shown in Figure 2. The pressure was kept constant at 2 tons.

Figure 2: Schematic illustration of composite fabrication from alternating layers of the fully cured vitrimer single plies and thermoset prepregs of different initial cure states.

2.2 Thermal Analysis

Dynamic thermal analyses were done with Netzsch DSC 214 Polyma. Samples were prepared in concavus aluminum pans with lids pierced. The temperature was ramped from 30 to 320°C at a rate of 10°C/min under nitrogen. The data was processed with Proteus Analysis version 7.1.0 (2017, Netzsch-Geratebau GmbH, Germany).

Thermal stability and degradation studies were done with Netzsch TG 209 F1 Libra. Samples were prepared in Al₂O₃ pans. The temperature was ramped from 30 to 800°C at a rate of 10°C/min under nitrogen or air. The data was processed with Proteus Analysis version 8.0.2 (2020).

Dynamic thermomechanical analysis was conducted with TA Q800 DMA. Samples with dimensions of 12×32×3 mm³ were prepared and placed in a single cantilever fixture. A force amplitude of 15 μm with frequency of 1 Hz was applied from 30°C to 300°C at a rate of 3°C/min. The data was processed with Universal Analysis version 4.5A.

2.3 Mechanical Testing

Flexural testing was conducted with Instron 68TM-50 Universal Testing Machine. Flexural tests were based on ASTM D790 wherein samples with dimensions 12×65×3 mm³ were prepared and placed on support beams with a span of 48 mm. At least 10N was applied at a rate of 1.3 mm/min until fracture. The data was processed with BlueHill version 4.38.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Preparation of Single Plies of Various Initial Cure States

Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) was employed to assess the initial cure states of the uncured, partially cured, and fully cured thermoset prepregs, as well as the fully cured vitrimer single ply used in laminate fabrication. The DSC thermograms of the uncured and partially cured prepregs exhibited exothermic peaks beginning around 130°C, indicating that the curing reactions were incomplete. Notably, the uncured prepreg displayed a significantly larger exothermic peak area compared to the partially cured sample, reflecting a lower extent of initial cure of the former. The absence of a glass transition in the partially cured prepreg further confirms that it had not reached full cure. In contrast, both the fully cured thermoset prepreg and vitrimer single ply exhibited clear glass transition temperatures, consistent with complete network formation. These findings verify that the prepreg samples represent distinct cure states, validating their selection for studying the influence of initial cure on performance of the resulting laminates and the efficiency of vitrimers in rejuvenating out-of-date or improperly cured thermoset prepregs.

Figure 3: (a) DSC and (b) DMA thermograms of vitrimer and thermoset prepregs showing different stages of initial cure.

To further evaluate the curing states of the thermoset prepregs and the vitrimer single ply, dynamic mechanical analysis was performed, as illustrated in Figure 3. The $\tan \delta$ and storage modulus curves for the uncured prepreg, Unc VTCF, are characteristic of an uncured network, displaying small $\tan \delta$ peaks at around 131°C and 149°C. These peaks are followed by an increase in storage modulus, indicative of ongoing curing reactions during the thermal sweep. The partially cured prepreg, Par VTCF, exhibited a broad $\tan \delta$ curve extending from approximately 60°C to 200°C, suggesting continued curing throughout the analysis along with glass transition. This is further supported by an increase in the storage modulus following the broad peak, similar to the uncured sample, further confirming in situ network formation during the analysis. In contrast, the fully cured prepreg, Ful VTCF, and the vitrimer single ply, *p*VAPI-DETDA, both displayed symmetrical, single $\tan \delta$ peaks, signifying that their polymer networks were homogeneous and fully cured. Their storage modulus curves reveal a distinct glass transition followed by a rubbery plateau, further confirming their fully cured state. The measured glass transition temperatures, T_g , were 165°C for Ful VTCF and 192°C for *p*VAPI-DETDA. Notably, the ambient storage modulus and T_g of the vitrimer single ply exceeded that of Ful VTCF, suggesting that the selected vitrimer formulation does not compromise—and may even enhance—the thermal and mechanical performance of the resulting composite. This finding supports the suitability of the vitrimer for high-performance composite applications. Additionally, the broader and less intense $\tan \delta$ peak observed for *p*VAPI-DETDA, compared to Ful VTCF, implies the presence of additional molecular motions at elevated temperatures. This broadening can be attributed to dynamic bond exchange reactions inherent to vitrimers, in addition to conventional segmental motion of the polymer chains. Overall, the DMA results clearly demonstrate the distinct stages of cure in the prepregs under investigation, confirming that the starting materials possess varying degrees of cure, which is essential for this work.

3.2 Fiber-Resin Content of Laminates

To determine the resin content of composites fabricated from alternating layers of the fully cured imine-epoxy vitrimer, *p*VAPI-DETDA, and DGEBA-DETDA prepregs in uncured, partially cured, or fully cured states, thermogravimetric analysis was employed. The analysis was initially performed under oxidative conditions to ensure complete degradation of the resin matrix. At 600°C, the carrier gas was switched from air to nitrogen to inhibit oxidation of the carbon fiber. The mass of the carbon fiber was estimated from the residual mass. All laminates exhibited char yields of approximately 70%, indicating a consistent composition with around 30% resin and 70% fiber content.

Figure 4: TGA thermograms of laminates from alternating layers of the fully cured vitrimer single plies and thermoset prepregs of different initial cure states under air atmosphere followed by nitrogen atmosphere.

3.3 Thermal Properties of Laminates

To assess how the initial cure state of thermoset prepregs influences the thermal properties of the resulting laminates, differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) was performed. All laminates exhibited DSC thermograms with no significant residual exothermic peaks, confirming complete curing across samples. The measured glass transition temperatures (T_g) were all comparable, around 140°C , indicating that the initial degree of cure of the prepregs had minimal impact on the final thermal properties of the composites. Interestingly, the laminate fabricated from the partially cured prepreg showed the highest T_g among the samples. This result may be attributed to the identical chemical composition of all laminates. Although variations in the initial cure states would typically lead to differences in crosslinking density after final curing, these differences were not reflected in the T_g values. This suggests that the fully cured vitrimer matrix may have facilitated effective network integration and crosslinking, contributing to the recovery or uniformity of thermal properties regardless of the prepreg's initial cure state.

Figure 5: (a) DSC and (b) DMA thermograms of laminates from alternating layers of the fully cured vitrimer single plies and thermoset prepregs of different initial cure states.

To evaluate and compare the mechanical performance and viscoelastic behavior of laminates fabricated from prepregs with varying degrees of cure and vitrimer single plies, dynamic mechanical analysis was performed, as presented in Figure 5. All laminates exhibited symmetrical single peaks in their $\tan \delta$ curves, indicating homogenous polymer networks and complete curing. The measured glass transition temperatures, T_g , were 169°C for the laminate from uncured prepregs, 177°C for that from partially cured prepregs, and 167°C for that from fully cured prepregs. These T_g values are relatively close, in alignment with differential scanning calorimetry results, and suggest effective integration of the vitrimer into all prepreg states, contributing to enhanced crosslinking. Furthermore, the T_g values lie between those of the neat DGEBA–DETDA and *p*VAPI–DETDA vitrimer single plies, reinforcing successful vitrimer integration.

Notably, the T_g of the laminate from partially cured prepregs was the highest among the three, implying that vitrimers can significantly improve the performance and usability of out-of-date prepregs with residual reactivity. Conversely, the lowest T_g was observed in the laminate from fully cured prepregs, which is consistent with their reduced number of available functional groups for vitrimer bonding, thereby limiting network rejuvenation. These observations highlight the influence of the initial cure state of the prepreg on the ability of the vitrimer to bond and rejuvenate the out-of-date prepreg. This trend is consistent with the storage modulus results. The storage moduli of laminates from uncured and partially cured prepregs were comparable, while the laminate from fully cured prepregs exhibited a lower modulus. Similarly, crosslink density followed the same pattern with the highest crosslink density observed was in the laminate from uncured prepregs, followed by that from partially cured prepregs, and with the lowest in the fully cured group. The comparable storage modulus and crosslinking density between the uncured and partially cured systems indicate that the presence of available reactive groups is critical for vitrimer integration. Moreover, this shows that a vitrimer single

ply is effective in restoring the mechanical properties and thermal properties of out-of-date prepregs without significant performance loss.

The effect of the prepreg cure state on the thermal stability and degradation behavior of resulting laminates was assessed with thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) under both non-oxidative and oxidative conditions, as illustrated in Figure 6. All laminates, prepared by alternating layers of fully cured imine-epoxy vitrimer single plies and DGEBA-DETDA prepregs in uncured, partially cured, or fully cured states, exhibit unimodal degradation within the range of 350–450°C. This degradation is primarily attributed to the thermolytic cleavage of C–N and C–O bonds. The onset degradation temperatures were measured to be 351°C, 353°C, and 359°C for laminates containing uncured, partially cured, and fully cured prepregs, respectively. A similar trend is observed in the maximum degradation temperatures, i.e., 375°C, 378°C, and 387°C for laminates from uncured, partially cured, and fully cured prepregs, respectively. The narrow range of these values suggests that the initial cure state of the prepregs has only a minor influence on the thermal stability and degradation behavior of the resulting composites. These properties are predominantly dictated by the chemical composition and molecular structure. Since all composites were fabricated from the same epoxy and hardener systems in fixed ratios, the observed thermal behaviors are consistent. Nonetheless, the observed differences align with the curing state, where a higher initial degree of cure correlates with slightly elevated onset and peak degradation temperatures. Laminates incorporating fully cured prepregs demonstrated the highest thermal stability, followed by those with partially cured and uncured prepregs. These elevated degradation temperatures which are significantly above typical service conditions indicate excellent thermal stability, affirming the suitability of these materials for high-performance structural applications. Notably, the degradation temperatures of the composites are substantially higher than those of the pure vitrimers, suggesting that interlayering with conventional high-performance thermosets can enhance the thermal stability of vitrimer-based systems. In terms of char yield, all laminates show values around 70%, indicating a resin content of approximately 30%. This consistency confirms that comparisons reflect the effect of cure state rather than differences in resin loading. In conclusion, the cure state of the out-of-date prepregs has only a minor impact on the thermal degradation behavior of the composites under non-oxidative environments. Even in laminates composed of fully cured prepregs and vitrimer single plies, degradation temperatures remain around 380 °C, reinforcing their potential for high-performance applications.

Figure 6: TGA thermograms of laminates from alternating layers of the fully cured vitrimer single plies and thermoset prepregs of different initial cure states under nitrogen atmosphere.

Under oxidative conditions as shown in Figure 4, the thermograms of the laminates composed of alternating layers of fully cured imine-epoxy vitrimer single plies and uncured prepregs display an initial unimodal degradation between 350–450°C, primarily resulting from the thermolytic cleavage of

C–N and C–O bonds just like under non-oxidative conditions. In contrast, laminates incorporating partially or fully cured prepregs exhibit bimodal degradation within the 300–450°C range. This bimodal behavior suggests that oxidative conditions amplify the influence of voids and interfacial adhesion differences introduced during laminate fabrication. The presence of partially or fully cured prepregs likely leads to poorer adhesion, increased void formation, or both. The onset degradation temperatures are 353°C, 354°C, and 349°C for laminates containing uncured, partially cured, and fully cured prepregs, respectively. Maximum degradation temperatures are 370°C, 375°C, and 385°C for laminates containing uncured, partially cured, and fully cured prepregs, respectively. While the overall trends are consistent with those observed under non-oxidative conditions, the laminate derived from fully cured prepregs displays the lowest onset degradation temperature. This indicates that, under oxidative conditions, the influence of defects such as poor interfacial adhesion and voids is more pronounced. Nevertheless, the difference in onset degradation temperatures compared to laminates prepared from uncured and partially cured prepregs remains relatively minor. A secondary degradation peak appears around 550°C in all samples, corresponding to the oxidative decomposition of residues formed by the epoxy networks which is not observed under non-oxidative conditions. To estimate resin content, the carrier gas was switched from air to nitrogen at 600°C to prevent oxidation of the carbon fiber. All laminates exhibited char yields near 70%, indicating a consistent resin content of approximately 30% and confirming that thermal behavior differences arise from prepreg cure state rather than formulation differences. In summary, the cure state of aged prepregs has only a minor effect on the thermal degradation behavior and stability of the laminates under both oxidative and inert conditions. Even laminates composed of fully cured prepregs and vitrimer plies degrade at high temperatures, 370–385°C, reinforcing their potential for high-performance structural applications.

3.4 Mechanical Properties of Laminates

The mechanical performance of composites fabricated from alternating layers of imine-epoxy vitrimer single plies and DGEBA-DETDA prepregs that were initially uncured, partially cured, or fully cured were evaluated via three-point bending tests, as illustrated in Figure 7. All laminates exhibited brittle failure, as indicated by the abrupt fracture observed in the stress–strain curves.

The flexural moduli for laminates fabricated from uncured, partially cured, and fully cured prepregs were 105 GPa, 105 GPa, and 98 GPa, respectively. These values are similar in value, suggesting that the modulus is predominantly dictated by the carbon fiber reinforcement, given its significantly higher stiffness relative to the matrix materials. Both the vitrimer and thermoset matrices are inherently stiff materials, which also contributes to the consistently high modulus values. The identical moduli of the laminates from uncured and partially cured prepregs, and their slightly higher values compared to those from fully cured prepregs, indicate that the vitrimer is highly effective in restoring or maintaining mechanical performance across varying cure states. When functional groups are available, as in the uncured and partially cured states, the vitrimer can form covalent bonds across the interface through transamination with unreacted amine groups, preserving interfacial integrity and mechanical performance. The slightly lower modulus observed in the laminate from fully cured prepregs suggests some reduction in adhesion efficiency due to limited availability of functional groups; however, the value remains high, implying that good bonding was still achieved through interfacial chain diffusion and entanglement by the vitrimer. Interlaminar adhesion plays a critical role in the mechanical performance of fiber-reinforced composites. Strong bonding between adjacent plies enables efficient stress transfer and uniform load distribution during bending. In contrast, poor interfacial adhesion can result in stress concentration at ply interfaces, leading to delamination, premature cracking, and failure under flexural loads. Insufficient bonding compromises load transfer, causing reductions in both flexural strength and stiffness.

The flexural strengths of the laminates from uncured, partially cured, and fully cured prepregs were 1.3 GPa, 1.1 GPa, and 0.7 GPa, respectively. These results confirm that the vitrimer was able to bond effectively across all prepreg conditions, including the fully cured state. The comparable strengths between laminates from uncured and partially cured prepregs suggest that the vitrimer successfully

underwent transimination reactions with unreacted amine groups at the interface, promoting strong interfacial bonding. The reduced strength observed in the laminate from fully cured prepregs likely arises from limited chemical reactivity due to the scarcity of available functional groups. In this case, vitrimer adhesion may rely more heavily on physical chain diffusion and entanglement as well as secondary interactions across the interface. Despite this limitation, a strength of 0.7 GPa was achieved, indicating that the vitrimer can still form mechanically robust interfaces with fully cured thermosets. Moreover, the presence of voids can further compromise mechanical performance by serving as stress concentrators, reducing the effective load-bearing volume of the composite. Voids typically arise during fabrication due to limited resin flow, particularly when bonding to fully cured prepregs. These defects reduce flexural strength and stiffness and contribute to early crack initiation and propagation during loading. Hence, the effects of differences in initial cure states of the prepregs resulting in differences in adhesion efficiency and void formation likelihood are more pronounced in the measured values of the flexural strength compared to the flexural modulus.

Figure 7: (a) Representative flexural stress-strain curves, (b) flexural strength and modulus of laminates from alternating layers of the fully cured vitrimer single plies and thermoset prepregs of different initial cure states.

Importantly, the mechanical performance of the laminate fabricated from partially cured prepregs is nearly equivalent to that from fresh uncured prepregs. This finding underscores the capacity of vitrimers to rejuvenate prepregs that have undergone partial cure and become boardy. It highlights the potential of imine-based vitrimers in restoring and reprocessing out-of-date prepregs for high-performance structural applications. Additionally, the initial cure state of the prepreg critically influences the bonding efficacy of the vitrimer and the extent of void formation, both of which significantly impact the resulting mechanical properties. For high-performance carbon fiber composites, optimizing interlaminar adhesion and minimizing void content are essential to maximizing flexural strength, stiffness, and toughness. Weak bonding or high void density can severely degrade performance, underscoring the importance of interfacial engineering when integrating vitrimer systems with thermoset prepregs.

3.5 Microscopy of Laminates

To evaluate the effect of initial cure states on the consolidation of the layers, optical images were obtained. Microscopy shows good consolidation in all samples. However, voids are present. The number of voids also increased as the initial cure state was more towards full curing. This could also

be the reason for the lower mechanical properties observed. But adhesion between the vitrimer and thermoset prepregs can be seen from optical images even if the prepreg was initially fully cured. This indicates that vitrimers can adhere to thermosets at different initial stages of cure. They are able to diffuse and entangle across the interface aside from covalent interactions with unreacted groups at the surface.

Figure 8: Optical images of cross-sections of the carbon fibre composites fabricated from alternating layers of the fully cured vitrimer single plies and (a) partially cured or (b) fully cured thermoset prepregs.

4 CONCLUSIONS

In this study, we leveraged the inherent weldability of fully cured imine-epoxy vitrimers and assessed their effectiveness in rejuvenating improperly cured or out-of-date thermoset prepregs. Traditional thermoset prepregs require refrigerated storage and transport, making logistics complex and increasing material waste due to spoilage during power outages. To simulate these conditions, thermoset prepregs from diglycidyl ether of bisphenol A, a commercially available resin, were pre-cured at varying temperatures to represent different degrees of initial cure, then interleaved them with fully cured vitrimer carbon fiber single plies. The resulting composites were evaluated for their thermal and mechanical properties. The results demonstrate that the initial cure state of the thermoset prepregs plays a critical role in dictating the resulting laminate properties. Laminates made with partially cured prepregs, i.e., cured at 80°C, exhibited thermal and mechanical properties comparable to those made with freshly prepared prepregs. This indicates that the presence of residual reactive groups such as unreacted amines allows for transimination reactions at the interface, forming covalent bonds between the vitrimer and thermoset, and near-complete property recovery. In contrast, prepregs cured at 150°C, which are fully crosslinked and lack functional groups capable of undergoing transimination, resulted in laminates with reduced mechanical properties. In this case, bonding was limited to physical mechanisms such as interfacial chain diffusion and entanglement. Nevertheless, microscopy confirmed ply adhesion, and thermal properties remained comparable with those of laminates made from fresh or partially cured prepregs, indicating partial recovery and successful consolidation. These findings highlight the critical role of interfacial chemistry specifically the availability of dynamic covalent bonding sites in determining the efficiency of vitrimer-assisted rejuvenation. Fully cured vitrimers can still adhere to fully cured thermoset prepregs and provide property recovery to a notable extent, even in the absence of covalent bonding. This capability presents a promising strategy to extend the usability of out-of-date prepregs, reduce material waste, and alleviate the challenges associated with refrigerated transport in composites manufacturing.

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